

A Study on Land Degradation in India

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Land Degradation

Land degradation is a process in which the value of the biophysical environment is affected by one or more combination of human-induced processes acting upon the land. It is viewed as any change or disturbance to the land perceived to be deleterious or undesirable. Degradation may also result from population growth, urban sprawl industrial development, clear-cutting and deforestation, mining, environmental pollution changes in agriculture and forestry practices, overgrazing, poor farming practices, inappropriate irrigation and over drafting over-exploitation and soil erosion and solicitation land degradation can assume different levels viz; partial or complete destruction of vegetation or loss of soil mantle by erosion. Land degradation is a global problem, it is estimated that up to 40% of the world's agricultural land is seriously degraded.

Over the years, the India's landmass has suffered from different types of degradations. According to a report by ISRO's Space Application Centre, in the year 2011-2012, India's land degradation was observed 29.3 percent (96.4 million hectare) of total land. Almost 90 percent of the states experienced a rise in land degradation. Land degradation affects people and ecosystems across the country; therefore, it is essential to focus on the issue. In the present study an attempt is made to study and analyze the land degradation in India, in the context causes, effects and measurement policies.

Land degradation and desertification in India

India has about 18% of world's population and only 2% of geographical area. The increasing human population has reduced the availability of land over the years. The per capita availability of land has declined from 0.89 to 0.37 hectare from 1951 to 1991 and is projected to slide down to 0.20 hectare in 2035. As far as agricultural land is concerned the per capita availability of land has declined from 0.48 hectare to 0.16 hectare from 1951 to 1991 and is likely to decline further to 0.08 hectare in 2035.

Out of 329 million hectares of geographical area of India, about 141 million hectares is Net Cultivated Area. Out of this, about 57 million hectare (40%) is irrigated and the remaining 85 million ha. (60%) is rainfed.

This area is generally subject to wind and water erosion and is in different stages of degradation for subjecting to intensive agricultural production. So, land degradation is very serious matter, it needs improvement in terms of its productivity per unit of land and per unit of water for optimum production.

The State-wise details of extent of various kind of lands degradation are given in following table.

Table 2: Major State-wise extent of various kinds of Land Degradation in India
(As per NBSS&LUP-ICAR-2005 on the Scale of 1:250,000) (Area in thousand hectares)

Sr. No.	Name of the state	Water erosion	Wind erosion	Water logging	Salinity/alkal.	Soil acidity	Complex Problem	Degraded Area	Geo. Area	Degraded area (%)
1	Andhra Pradesh	11518	0	1896	517	905	156	14992	27050	54.5
2	Arunachal Pradesh	2372	0	176	0	1955	0	4503	8374	53.8
3	Himachal Pradesh	2718	0	1303	0	157	0	4178	5567	75.0
4	Kerala	76	0	2098	0	138	296	2608	3886	67.1
5	M.P.+Chhattisgarh	17883	0	359	46	6796	1126	26210	44345	59.1
6	Maharashtr	11179	0	0	1056	517	303	33055	30771	42.4
7	Mizoram	137	0	0	0	1050	694	1881	2108	89.2
8	Meghalaya	137	0	7	0	1030	34	1208	2243	53.9
9	Nagaland	390	0	0	0	127	478	995	1658	60.0
10	Tripura	121	0	191	0	203	113	628	1049	59.9
11	U.P.+Uttar-akhand	11392	212	2350	1370	0	0	15324	29441	52.0
Grand Total		93678	9483	14299	5944	16033	7381	146820	328602	29.3
Grand Total (Million ha.)		93.68	9.48	14.30	5.94	16.03	7.38	146.82	328.60	

Source: 1. There are several estimates for the extent of degraded lands reported by various agencies in the country. These estimates vary largely due to variation in approaches and methodologies of estimation. In absence of comprehensive and periodic scientific surveys, the figures reported by National Bureau of Soil Survey & Land Use Planning, Nagpur based on studies and several estimates (2005) for various land degradation have been considered as logically concluded and are being used for various purposes.

2. www.stantram.com.

Major state-wise land degradations and various kinds of land degradations are shown in above table. It is observed that in India, 96.4 million hectares area (29.3 percent) to the total is degraded. Water erosion is prime reason for land degradation. Out of total degraded land, 63.81 percent land is degraded due to water erosion. Soil acidity and water logging placed second and third rank for land degradation with 16.03 and 14.30 million hectares land degraded due to these reasons. Wind erosion caused 9.48 million hectares land degraded. 5.94 million hectares land degraded because of land salinity. Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Karnataka, Ladakh, Jharkhand, Odisha, Madhya Pradesh and Telangana states show highest degraded land. The causes for land degradation are explained as follows;

Soil erosion: when the soil is washed away through excessive rain, flood or wind soil erosion take place. It occurs because deforestation, overgrazing and faulty cultivation. It is difficult to calculate the total national soil loss as a result of erosion but loss is estimated to be around 6,000 to 7,000 million tones of soil, which in terms of major nutrient, such as nitrogen, phosphorous, and potassium.

Deforestation, Clear-cutting: The removal of trees without sufficient reforestation has resulted in damage to habitat, biodiversity loss and aridity. Deforested regions typically incur significant adverse soil erosion and frequently degrade into wasteland.

Clear-cutting can have major negative impacts, both for humans and local flora and fauna. A study from the University of Oregon found that in certain zones, areas that were clear cut had nearly three times the amount of erosion due to slides. When the roads required by the clear-cutting were factored in, the increase in slide activity appeared to be about 5 times greater compared to nearby forested areas. Clear-cutting can also lead to an increased possibility of rapid runoff, loss of economic sustainability in that no timber products are available for a long time after clear-cutting, loss of habitat for some wildlife species.

In India there is viciously attacked and destroyed country's forest in last 60 years since Independence. According to FAO, India was supposed to have lost 3.4 million hectares of forest land between 1951 and 1972 alone. The process of deforestation has continued till today. A recent report prepared by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources mentions that India has lost nearly 205 million hectares mangrove forest in this century alone-these remarkable forests can grow on marginal lands, and survive soil infertility, water logging and salinity and high winds.

Overgrazing: Overgrazing is the grazing of natural pastures at stocking intensities above the livestock carrying capacity; the resulting decrease in the vegetation cover is a leading cause of wind and water erosion. In India, the government has badly neglected grazing land. According to land use statistics, 11 million hectares of land in the country are permanent grazing land.

The effects of overgrazing on the environment are alarming. Land degradation due to overgrazing has led to *desert-like* condition in many parts of country. Overgrazing reduces the usefulness, productivity, and biodiversity of the land and is one cause of desertification and erosion.

Mismanagement of irrigation: Agricultural activities that can cause land degradation include shifting cultivation without adequate fallow periods, absence of soil conservation measures, fertilizer use, and a host of possible problems arising from faulty planning or management of irrigation.

Even though India is one of the wettest countries of the world, it is not able to hold all the rain water. Faulty water management, deforestation and denudation, a large portion of monsoon water disappears into sea as surface run-off. It's also caused to water logging, water salinity, soil acidity etc. Above table shows that nearly 36-million-hectare area of the country suffer from water logging, water salinity and soil acidity.

Water logging: Water logging has become a serious problem and menace in Punjab and Haryana. This problem also exists in various irrigation projects, U.P., West Bengal, Maharashtra, Gujarat, A.P. etc. Above table shows that more than 14 million hectares area is under water logging in India.

Land Salinity: The soil contains certain salts which are harmful for the plants. As long as these salt lie in deep in the earth, there is no problem. But if it brought to surface, it harms to crop and making cultivation impossible. In India, A major portion of the salt- affected lands lies in fertile Indo-Gangetic plains of Punjab, Haryana and U.P. In India 5.94 area is under land salinity.

Soil acidification is the buildup of hydrogen cation, also called protons, reducing the soil PH. This happens when a proton donor is added to the soil. The donor can be an acid, such as nitric acid and sulfuric acid. It can also be a compound such as aluminum sulfate, which reacts in the soil to release protons. Many nitrogen compounds, which are added as fertilizer, also acidify soil over the long term because they produce the ammonium ion which is a proton donor.

Land pollution: Land pollution is the degradation of Earth's land surfaces often caused by human activities and their misuse of land resources. It occurs when waste is not disposed properly. Health hazard disposal of

urban and industrial wastes, exploitation of minerals, and improper use of soil by inadequate agricultural practices are a few factors.

India's uncontrolled industries increased air, water and industrial waste. Industrial waste is a type of waste produced by industrial activity, such as that of factories, mills and mines. It has existed since the outset of the industrial revolution. According to one estimate, the present annual generation of solid waste in Indian cities and towns has increased from 6 million tonnes to 48 million tonnes from 1947 to 1997, and is expected to 300 million tonnes by the middle of this century.

Population pressure: The role of population factors in land degradation processes obviously occurs in the context of the underlying causes. In the region, in fact, it is indeed one of the two along with land shortage, and land shortage itself ultimately is a consequence of continued population growth in the face of the finiteness of land resources. In the context of land shortage the growing population pressure, during 1980-1990, has led to decreases in the already small areas of agricultural land per person in six out of eight countries (14% for India and 22% for Pakistan).

Schemes/Programmes for Development of Degraded Lands in India

The information on the extent of soil degradation in the country has been assessed by various agencies. The estimates of these agencies vary widely i.e. 63.9 m. ha. to 187.0 m. ha., due to different approaches in defining degraded soils and adopting various criteria for delineation.

The problems of land degradation are prevalent in many forms throughout the country. Soon after independence India adopted various schemes and programmes for development of degraded land, such schemes and programmes as follows.

- i. Various Watershed Programmes:** After independence Various Watershed Development Programmes are being implemented by Govt. of India. These programmes are namely, (i) National Watershed Development Project for Rainfed Areas (NWDPA), (ii) Reclamation & Development of Alkali & Acid Soil (RADAS), (iii) Soil Conservation in the Catchments of River Valley Project & Flood Prone River (RVP & FPR), (iv) Watershed Development Project in Shifting Cultivation Areas (WDPSA) (v) Drought Prone Area Programme (DPAP) (vi) Integrated Wasteland Development Programme (IWDP) and National Afforestation & Eco – Development Project (NAEP). With above, few Externally Aided Projects (EAPs) are being implemented with technical and financial assistance of external agencies. Since 1950 to Tenth Five Year Plan, 50.89 million hectares area has been developed with an expenditure of Rs.19251.22 Crore.
- ii. The Natural Resource Management Division (NRMD):** NRMD implementing various programmes, for development of degraded land, in which *central sector programme of 'Soil & Land Use Survey of India (SLUSI), The Soil Conservation Training Centre at Damodar Valley Corporation, Hazaribagh', special Central Assistance to State Plan Scheme on Watershed Development Project in Shifting Cultivation Areas (WDPSA*

(SLUSI)' facilitates various types of soil surveys of catchments/watersheds. The organization is also engaged in preparation of district-wise map of land degradation.

SCTC-DVC (Non-Plan) is being finance and implemented as non-plan scheme for imparting training / capacity building of the officials working for soil & water conservation programme in the State Governments. During 2008-09, an amount of Rs.0.40 crore is allocated for conducting various short & medium training courses.

RADAS is being implemented in the states, where alkalinity exists. Since inception up to 10th plan 6.59 lakhs ha. area has been reclaimed.

- iii. National Watershed Development Project for Rain-fed Areas (NWDPR):** This programme was launched in 1990-91 in 28 states and 2 Union territories. It is based on integrated watershed management and sustainable farming. Since inception to 10th plan 94.02 lakhs ha. area have been developed under this scheme.
- iv. Rain-fed Area Development Programme (RADP):** In the year 2007-08 the union finance minister announced Rain-fed Area Development Programme. Under this programme, it is expected to cover 30 lakhs ha. area during 11th plan period, the budget provision of Rs. 3500 Crore for implementing of this scheme.
- v. Perspective Plan for Development of Degraded Lands during XI Plan:** The 11th plan (2007-12) has focused attention on 60 percent of unirrigated and rain-fed land. Watershed management, rain water harvesting and ground water recharge will augmented water availability. The 11th plan estimated a total investment of Rs. 25840 Crore for the development an area 32.05 million hectares area under various schemes. The following table shows the details of target and outlay proposed under various watershed development programmes for xi plan.

Conclusion

Land, a non-renewable resource, is central to all primary production system. It serves as storage for water and nutrients required for plants and other living micro-macro-organisms. The demand for food, energy and other human requirements depends upon the land. But land resources are limited. Over the years, the country's landmass has suffered from different types of degradations. In the widest context, land not in its original undisturbed state is referred as degraded or damaged land. Degradation may also result from population growth, urban sprawl industrial development, deforestation, environmental pollution, overgrazing, poor farming practices, inappropriate irrigation and over drafting, soil erosion etc. Therefore, it needs to preservation and improvement of the productivity of land.

Over the years, the India's landmass has suffered from different types of degradations. More than 53 percent areas of the country suffer from land degradation. But the problem of land degradation can prevalent. In India the problems of land degradation are prevalent in many forms. Soon after independence India adopted various schemes and programmes for development of degraded land.

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